

Review

Hydrogen Sulfide in Balneology: Physiology, Evidence, and Clinical Translation

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Abstract

This review integrates the biology and clinical translation of hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) in balneology. It frames H₂S as a gasotransmitter with dual chemical and biological actions and summarizes the H₂S/HS⁻ equilibrium as a function of pH, temperature, and oxygenation, which governs bioaccessibility in sulfurous waters. Endogenous and exogenous sources, transport, and mitochondrial catabolism are outlined, together with core cellular mechanisms: protein persulfidation; activation of Nrf2/ARE; modulation of NF-κB; regulation of ion channels; and engagement of PI3K/Akt, MAPK/ERK, and Wnt pathways, plus epigenetic interactions with HDACs and sirtuins. Preclinical and clinical evidence in dermatology, musculoskeletal disease, and respiratory care is synthesized, alongside metabolic, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, and renal effects. Technical aspects that preserve the bioactive fraction of H₂S while meeting environmental safety limits are highlighted. Routes of administration (bathing, peloids, inhalation, and drinking cures) and key operational parameters are described. Overall, the review links physicochemical and molecular foundations with clinical indications for sulfurous waters and derivatives and identifies opportunities for research and development in H₂S donors and thermal cosmetics without extrapolating beyond the available data.

Keywords: hydrogen sulfide; sulfurous waters; balneotherapy; dermatology; rheumatology; inhalation therapy; spa therapy; sulfur springs; peloids; epigenetics

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1. Introduction

Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), previously considered merely a toxic byproduct of anaerobic metabolism, is now recognized as an endogenous gasotransmitter with important physiological functions, comparable to nitric oxide (NO) and carbon monoxide (CO) [1,2].

Over the past two decades, H₂S has been identified as a critical modulator of cellular signaling, redox homeostasis, inflammation, and epigenetic modulation with an increasing interest in its therapeutic applications, particularly in the context of balneotherapy with sulfurous medicinal waters [1,3,4]. Recent years have witnessed a surge in discoveries related to the signaling roles of polysulfides and their superior redox potential compared to H₂S, prompting reconsideration of therapeutic sulfur species in balneology. In parallel, novel H₂S delivery technologies and deeper insights into mitochondrial targets such